

ABDULLA AVLONI

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Abstract

This article discusses the role of education in the work of Abdullah Avlani. Education is the most important stimulus in the works of the writer.

Key words: Enlightener, teacher, publisher, writer of instructive books for children, educator of Uzbek culture, national writer and poet.

Abdulla Avlani is one of the founders of Uzbek children's literature, national theater and drama. His wonderful words: "To be a bright ray for others, to radiate this light yourself - this is the highest happiness that a person can achieve" became the motto for many generations of people. Abdullah Avlani was born on July 12, 1878 in the family of a handicraft weaver. He studied at an old type school, then at a madrasah.

Having studied Arabic, Persian and Russian, he read the works of thinkers in the original language. He was a prominent representative of the Jadid movement, which he joined in 1904. The word "jadid" in Arabic means "new". The main idea of the Jadids was to create a progressive society in Turkestan, a national democratic state, which could be achieved by raising the level of socio-political and cultural consciousness of people, especially young people. Their tasks included the creation and expansion of a network of new method schools, various educational associations, theater troupes, the publication of newspapers and magazines, and the training of the best representatives of talented youth abroad. The opening of new method schools made it possible to teach children of the local population to read and write, to form a new worldview in them. Along with the basics of Islam, these schools taught arithmetic, history, geography and natural history. In the classroom, teachers tried to acquaint their students with the achievements of the East and West.

Abdullah Avlani showed great dedication in spreading enlightenment and education. In 1908 he opened a new method school in Mirabad. In schools, they talked about the earth, people, nature, stars, along with the basics of religion, they taught secular sciences. New textbooks were needed to spread the new system of education. In the period from 1909 to 1917, he wrote over 10

manuals, which played a great role in the history of the Uzbek school and the development of pedagogical thought.

Pedagogy was raised to a new level. His book "The First Teacher" was intended for elementary school and adhered to the principle: from simple to complex. The book "The Second Teacher" was a continuation and development of the first book.

In 1917, the book "Turkic Flower Garden or Morality" was published, in which Avlani sets out his social, moral and educational views. Creating it, he relied on folk pedagogy. Education, in his opinion, begins at birth and continues until the end of life. Education is the responsibility of the father, teacher, mudaris (mentor) and the state. The Enlightener attached great importance to education, talent, breadth

worldview, personality of the teacher. The strength and breadth of the student's thinking depends on the breadth of the teacher's views. Great importance is given in the book to the issues of patriotism. According to Avlani, the Fatherland "...cannot be simply loved, it must be proud of. Love should be expressed directly in deeds and the desire to make our homeland more perfect. Motherland is sacred, like a mother. Avlani devoted a whole chapter to his native language and literature.

He writes that language and literature are an indicator of the existence of every nation on earth. Losing the national language means losing the spirit of the nation. Abdullah Avlani urged to protect and preserve the purity of the language. The whole book is divided into two parts: this is a description of good and bad qualities. There are 18 chapters devoted to the description of bad qualities. Avlani put the freedom of the motherland above all else. The only way that could lead to it is knowledge and enlightenment. This book left a noticeable mark in the development of pedagogy at the beginning of the 20th century and in the development of the social and aesthetic thinking of young people.

Avlani wanted Turkestan to prosper and express confidence that friendship, truth and justice would prevail. Abdullah Avlani made a huge contribution to the Jadid movement, it was thanks to his works that the world got acquainted with Jadid Uzbek literature.

In 1925-1930, he served as head of the department of "Language and Literature" at the Central Asian University. In 1927, for special merits in the cause of education, he was awarded the title of "Hero of Labor", and in 1930 - the honorary title of "Shock Worker of Public Education".

Abdullah Avlani opened schools, strove for universal education, education of youth on the basis of advanced ideas. His works left a noticeable mark on the development of pedagogical thought at the beginning of the 20th century. Everything that the great teacher of the Uzbek people wrote about is still relevant now, in the age of information and communication technologies, when every student must understand the role of education in his life.

Использованная литература:

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